

FULL STUDY PROTOCOL:

Measurement Properties of Supplement Intake PROMs in Athletes: A Systematic Review based on COSMIN guidelines.

1. Introduction / Background

Supplement consumption is a widespread practice among athletes and requires rigorous assessment due to potential health risks, including excessive nutrient intake beyond tolerable upper intake levels (ULs) and inadvertent exposure to contaminants not declared on supplement labels. Accurate assessment of supplement intake is therefore essential for research and clinical practice in sports nutrition.

Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) are commonly used to assess supplement intake in athletic populations; however, the validity and measurement quality of these instruments vary considerably. To date, no systematic review has comprehensively evaluated the measurement properties and methodological quality of PROMs designed to assess sport and dietary supplement intake in athletes in accordance with the COSMIN methodology.

Therefore, the aim of this systematic review is to identify valid PROMs developed to assess supplement intake in athletes, summarize the available evidence on their measurement properties, evaluate their methodological quality using COSMIN criteria, and formulate evidence-based recommendations to support the selection of appropriate instruments for supplement intake assessment in athletic populations.

2. Methods

2.1. Search Strategy

A systematic literature search will be conducted in accordance with the PRISMA-COSMIN guidelines for systematic reviews of patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) using two electronic databases: PubMed/MEDLINE and Scopus. The review protocol is registered in PROSPERO prior to data extraction, following pilot testing of the screening process to assess feasibility.

The search strategy was developed based on four key domains of the research question: (1) the construct of interest, (2) the target population, (3) the type of instrument, and (4) measurement properties. The construct of supplement intake was defined as the self-reported consumption of dietary, nutritional, or sports supplements intended to enhance health, performance, or recovery, including information on supplement type, frequency, dosage, quantity, and pattern of use. The target population comprised athletes, defined as individuals who participate in organized sport and engage in regular training and competition, at any competitive level (recreational to elite).

Search terms related to PROMs, questionnaires, and measurement properties were included to identify studies describing the development or evaluation of instruments assessing

supplement intake in athletes. Standardized self-reported questionnaires and interviewer-administered instruments were considered eligible PROMs.

The full electronic search strategy is provided in the PROSPERO registration and has been made publicly available via Zenodo along with the search files

The total number of retrieved records will be screened independently by two reviewers using Rayyan (Rayyan Systems Inc.). In case of disagreement, a resolution will be made by a third reviewer. To minimize the risk of excluding relevant studies, no studies will be automatically rejected based on Rayyan's machine-learning predictions, and all duplicates will be deleted manually. The study selection process will be documented using a PRISMA-COSMIN flow diagram, including reasons for exclusion at the full-text stage. Only studies reporting the development or evaluation of at least one measurement property of a PROM, as defined by COSMIN, will be eligible for inclusion.

During full-text screening, the reference lists of studies that used previously validated PROMs without evaluating measurement properties will be examined to identify additional relevant validation studies. Any eligible studies identified through backward citation tracking will be reported in the PRISMA flow diagram under "references from full-text screening".

2.2. Eligibility criteria

Eligible studies must include athletes, defined as participants of any sport modality and competitive level, aged 16 years or older.

Included studies must either describe the development of an athlete-specific questionnaire (PROM) intended to assess supplement intake or evaluate one or more measurement properties of an existing questionnaire assessing supplement intake in athletes. Studies that use a supplement intake questionnaire solely as a screening or data-collection tool, without reporting evidence on the development process or evaluation of any measurement properties as defined by COSMIN, will be excluded.

During the full-text screening phase, reference lists of excluded application studies will be examined to identify original development and validation studies of the PROMs used. Subscales within multidimensional PROMs, such as supplement sections of dietary assessment questionnaires, will be considered as separate PROMs only if validation of the subscale related to supplement intake is reported.

Knowledge–attitude–practice (KAP) questionnaires will be included for evaluation of the practice subscale only. Studies evaluating nutrition knowledge or attitudes alone will be excluded. Studies reporting the validation of PROMs intended to assess the intake of a specific dietary supplement in athletes will also be eligible. Adaptations of PROMs will be evaluated as separate PROMs if evidence of validation is provided.

2.3. Data management

Data from all included studies and patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) will be extracted using the COSMIN review management file, which provides an overview of PROM characteristics, feasibility, interpretability, and methodological quality. All COSMIN-defined measurement properties will be considered for assessment when reported in the included studies.

The methodological quality of each study will be evaluated using the COSMIN Risk of Bias checklist. Measurement property results will be rated as “sufficient”, “insufficient”, or “indeterminate” according to the COSMIN criteria for good measurement properties. For each PROM, results from studies with adequate methodological quality will be summarized per measurement property. When results across studies are conflicting, the overall rating will be classified as inconsistent in accordance with COSMIN guidance.

Subsequently, the quality of the evidence for each measurement property per PROM will be graded using a modified GRADE approach as “high”, “moderate”, “low”, or “very low”, reflecting the level of confidence that the estimated measurement property represents the true value. Finally, evidence-based recommendations will be formulated regarding the most appropriate PROMs for the assessment of supplement intake in athletes.